

Research Article

Effects of Soil Amendment on Foliar Disease of Different Cultivars of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogae*) In Owerri, Nigeria

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Abstract

*Effect of soil amendment on foliar disease of different cultivars of groundnut (*Arachis hypogae*) in Owerri, Nigeria. This experiment was carried out at Teaching and Research Farm, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria to identify options in cultivar as well as manure types which farmers could adopt in order to control or reduce the effect of foliar diseases of groundnut. Four different groundnut cultivars namely Samnut 21, Samnut 22, Samnut 23 and one local cultivar from Akure together with different manure types namely Poultry manure ten (10) tons/ha, Compost manure ten (10) tons/ha, NPK fertilizer three hundred (300) kg/ha and zero manure (Control) were used for the study. Split plot design was used in which groundnut cultivars and soil amendment constituted main plots and sub plots respectively. Data were collected on disease incidence and severity weekly beginning from four to eight weeks after treatment applications. Among the four cultivars, Samnut 22 had the least mean value for disease incidence of 15.6, 13.8, and 18.0, at 4, 6, and 8 weeks after planting respectively while Akure local had the highest mean value for disease incidence and severity of 25.8, 30.9, 40.1 and 1.0, 1.9, 3.3 at 4, 6 and 8 weeks after planting respectively. The application of Poultry manure had the least mean value of disease incidence and severity of 8.0, 9.2, 11.9 and 0.4, 1.4, 0.8 at 4, 6, and 8 weeks after planting respectively. Zero soil amendment (Control) had the highest mean value for disease incidence and severity of 31.9, 36.1, 46.9 and 1.8, 2.7, 3.4 at 4, 6, and 8 weeks after planting respectively. Application of poultry manure best suppressed leaf spot disease of groundnut. Samnut 22 consistently showed the least mean value for disease incidence and ranked second in mean for disease severity. This makes it most preferred to other cultivars in disease incidence as well as disease severity. Planting of Samnut 22 together with application of poultry manure reduced foliar disease of groundnut significantly.*

Key words: Amendment, cultivars, Samnut, compost manure, NPK fertilizer, incidence, severity.

Introduction

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogae* L) is an important cash crop in the tropical countries including Nigeria. The seed has great nutritional value; it contains 47% fat, 38.6% protein, 5.8% moisture, 1.8% carbohydrate, 3.7% crude fiber, and 3.8% ash (Atasie *et al.*, 2009). The seed is generally eaten raw, roasted or boiled while the oil extracted from the seed is used as cooking oil. Industrially, ground nut oil is used for making soap, cosmetics, lubricants as well as the production of groundnut cake which is used for making livestock feed (Ayele, 2010). In spite of the fact that the crop is well adapted and suited to various ecological zones, some factors still limit its productivity. Some of the factors include; soil, climate, cultivar, pests and diseases (Apan *et al.*, 2005). Some of such diseases include; bud necrosis also called spotted wilt, ring mosaic, groundnut mosaic, bunchy top chlorosis, ring mottle, bud blight, early and late leaf spot disease, (Shrestha and Srinivasan *et al.*, 2013). Early and late leaf spot disease caused by *Cercospora arachicola* and *Cercosporidium personatum* respectively reduce yield. (Subrahmanyam *et al.*, 2006). Current research efforts are directed toward epidemiology and management of these diseases. Particular areas of emphasis include determining the effect of partial resistance to *Cercospora arachicola* and *Cercosporidium personatum* on disease of early and late leaf spot of groundnut. Multiple studies are directed toward combination of cultural practices that suppress these diseases with moderately resistance cultivars and minimal pesticide inputs for managing these diseases in integrated disease management system. Some of these systems and projects are specifically geared toward organic groundnut production (Wann and Tubbs *et al.*, 2011). Foliar diseases are one of the most important factors contributing to low yield of groundnut in Africa and other parts of the world (Stone *et al.*, 2003).

Cercospora leaf spot diseases are generally present in many fields and their relative economic importance is determined by the disease severity, crop variety and environmental factors. Among the foliar diseases, epidemic of *Cercospora* leaf spot, popularly known as Tikka disease of groundnut in India and some other parts of the world including Africa is recorded frequently which lead to yield losses of 50% on unsprayed groundnuts (Gibbons, 2001). According to Subrahmanyam *et al.* (2006). *Cercospora* leaf spot cause 10% and 50% yield losses in disease resistance and susceptible varieties respectively. Reduction in yield is mainly attributed to premature drop and intense spotting of leaves and consequently resulting in reduction in photosynthetic activity in late leaf spot. Application of synthetic pesticides is an effective way of disease management (Kiran *et al.*, 2006). However, cost of the fungicides, pollution to soil, air, water, health hazards and development of resistance to these chemicals are diverting scientist's attention towards the practices which are cheap, ecologically safe and friendly (Bdliya and Aikali, 2008). Therefore, attention is shifted to the use of cultural practices

such as manuring, tillage, intercropping and crop rotation to reduce diseases in Nigeria and other groundnut growing parts of the world (Bailey and Lazarovits, 2003). Another management strategy involves the use of tactics that reduce the incidence and severity of disease by growing partially resistant cultivars. (Agrios, 2005). Many research works have been conducted on the use of chemical fertilizer to boost soil fertility as well as using synthetic pesticides to control foliar diseases of groundnut, with the sole aim of increasing the yield of groundnut. However, systemic studies relating to the use of cultural control methods like the use of poultry manure and compost which is cheap, ecologically safe and friendly are scarce. Epidemiology, cultivar-environment interaction and validity of disease management strategies are seldom available in groundnut growing belt of Nigeria. Thus this study was an attempt to identify options in cultivar vis-à-vis adaptation and disease resistance as well as cultural practices which farmers could adopt in order to control or reduce the effect of *Cercospora* leaf spot disease of groundnut so as to increase productivity in groundnut cultivation without adverse effect on environment and health.

Materials and Method

The research was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, located on latitude 5° 25'N and longitude 7° 1' E in the tropical rainforest zone of Southern Nigeria. The temperature ranges between 20°C and 32°C and mean annual rainfall of 2,500mm with high relative humidity of 84 - 100% (Nnaji, 2009). The research was carried out between May - August 2015. Three improved groundnut cultivars, Samnut 21, Samnut 22, and Samnut 23 obtained from National Seed Research Institute, Samaru, Zaria, Kaduna State and a local cultivar from Akure, Ondo State were also used. Ten (10) tons/ha Poultry manure, ten (10) tons/ha Compost manure, three hundred (300) kg/ha NPK fertilizer and zero manure (control) were the fertilizer types used for the experiment. The land was cleared and beds measuring 1 x 2m were made with hoe and spade, leaving a discard of 0.5m between plots and blocks to remove border effects. The treatments consisted of 4 x 4 factorial combinations of groundnut cultivars and different manure types arranged in a split-plot design. The groundnut cultivars constituted the main plots while soil amendments were the sub-plots. There were sixteen (16) treatment combinations replicated three (3) times. Seeds were planted at 20 x 20cm apart at two seeds per hole. The seedlings were later thinned to one plant per stand at one week after planting to give a plant population of 250,000 plants/ha.

Weeding was carried out manually by hand pulling and this was done twice before the final harvesting. Collection of data on disease in each treatment began at four weeks after

planting (WAP) and subsequent data were collected at two weeks interval up to eight weeks after planting.

i Disease Incidence: Determined by counting number of infected plants. This was expressed in percentage scale using the formula: $DI = \frac{\text{No of infected plants}}{\text{Total No of plants}} \times 100/1$.

ii Disease Severity: Using visual observation and Field Disease Severity Score Format according to Nutter *et al.*, (2006).

Disease Assessment	Scale	Interpretation
0	0	no infection
1 - 20	1	low infection
21 - 40	2	moderate infection
41 - 60	3	severe infection
61 - 80	4	very severe infection
81 - 100	5	completely infected

Data collected were analyzed statistically using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine treatment effect and means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range (DMR) at 5% probability Steel and Torrie, (1980).

Results and Discussion

Results

Disease Incidence

The result of the experiment showed that at fourth (4th) week after planting, local cultivar had the highest value of disease incidence but was not significantly higher than Samnut 23. Samnut 22 had the least value but significantly reduced leaf foliar disease incidence compared to other improved cultivars like Samnut21 and Samnut 23. But at sixth (6th), and eighth (8th) weeks after planting, planting local cultivar significantly increased foliar disease of groundnut compared with any other improved cultivars i.e. Samnut 21, Samnut 22 and Samnut 23. At 8 weeks after planting, planting of Samnut 22 reduced foliar disease most but not significantly reduced than Samnut 21. Thus, application of manure significantly reduced foliar disease incidence of groundnut (Table 1). Therefore, from the result above, it was noticed that planting of different cultivars had significant effect on groundnut leaf spot disease incidence (Table1). Planting of groundnut cultivars on soils without application of manure produced plants with highest value of foliar disease incidence and they were significantly higher when compared with the results of any other soil amended plot. Application of poultry manure significantly reduced foliar

disease incidence of groundnut compared to any other manure treatment and this reduction was followed by compost manure and NPK fertilizer. The same trend was observed at weeks 4, 6 and 8 after planting. Planting of local cultivar without manure significantly increased foliar disease incidence of groundnut, followed by planting of Samnut 23 without manure and local cultivar with NPK fertilizer respectively.

Disease Severity

Table 2 showed the result of effects of soil amendment on disease severity of four groundnut cultivars that was used for the experiment. The application of soil amendments to four different groundnut cultivars had no significant effect on foliar disease severity at 4th and 6th weeks after planting. Nevertheless, Akure local cultivar showed most severity with mean values of 1.0 and 1.9 respectively. But at 8th weeks after planting, Akure local cultivar was most affected by foliar disease compared to other cultivars i. e. Samnut 21, Samnut 22 and Samnut 23 while Samnut 22 cultivar was least affected by foliar disease. Also plots without any soil amendment (control of the experiment) consistently produced plants with most severe foliar disease. Akure local was not significant in disease severity at 4 weeks after planting but was more severe compared to any other soil amendment at 6 and 8 weeks after planting respectively. Application of poultry manure consistently produced plants with least disease severity at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting. But Akure local cultivar without any soil amendment (control) produced plants with the most foliar disease severity at 8 weeks after planting of (5.0), followed by Akure local with NPK fertilizer application (4.0). Samnut 22 with application of poultry manure had the least disease severity (0.1), followed by Samnut 22 with the application of compost manure (0.3) respectively.

Table 1: Effect of Soil Amendment on Disease Incidence of four Groundnut Cultivars

Groundnut cultivars	Soil Amendments														
	4WAP					6 WAP					8 WAP				
	Ctr	Comp	Fer.	Pm	Mean	Ctr.	Comp.	Fer.	Pm	Mean	Ctr	Comp	Fer.	Pm	Mean
Akure local	48.1	15.7	30.5	8.6	25.8	55.8	18.9	36.6	10.3	30.9	75.1	24.2	47.6	13.5	40.1
SamNut 21	27.8	11.9	17.8	8.3	16.5	30.0	13.1	19.6	9.2	18.0	38.9	17.1	25.5	11.9	23.3
SamNut 22	18.2	11.0	15.6	5.4	12.6	20.0	12.1	17.1	6.0	13.8	26.1	15.7	22.3	7.8	18.0
SamNut 23	33.3	20.9	20.6	9.5	21.1	36.6	22.9	22.7	11.1	23.3	47.6	29.8	29.5	14.4	30.3
Mean	31.9	14.9	21.2	8.0		36.1	16.8	24.0	9.2		46.9	21.7	31.2	11.9	
LSD 0.05 for (cultivar)				5.5					6.3					8.1	
LSD 0.05 for (Soil Amend)				4.3					4.8					6.3	
LSD 0.05 for (Cult x S. Amend)				8.6					9.8					12.7	

Key: Soil Amend = Soil Amendment

Cult = Cultivar

Ctr = Control

Comp = Compost

Fer = Fertilizer

Pm = Poultry manure

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Table 2: Effect of Soil Amendment on Disease Severity of four Groundnut Cultivars

Groundnut cultivars	Soil Amendments														
	4WAP					6 WAP					8 WAP				
	Ctr	Comp	Fer.	Pm	Mean	Ctr.	Comp.	Fer.	Pm	Mean	Ctr	Comp	Fer.	Pm	Mean
Akure local	2.0	1.0	0.3	0.7	1.0	2.7	2.0	1.3	1.7	1.9	5.0	2.3	4.0	1.7	3.3
SamNut 21	1.7	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.8	2.7	1.7	1.3	1.3	1.8	3.0	0.7	1.7	0.7	1.5
SamNut 22	1.7	0.7	1.0	0.3	0.9	2.7	1.7	2.0	1.3	1.9	2.0	0.3	1.7	0.1	1.0
SamNut 23	2.0	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.9	2.7	1.7	1.7	1.3	1.8	3.7	1.0	1.3	0.7	1.7
Mean	1.8	0.8	0.6	0.4		2.7	1.8	1.6	1.4		3.4	1.1	2.2	0.8	
LSD 0.05 for (cultivar)				Ns					0.8					0.6	
LSD 0.05 for (Soil Amend)				Ns					0.4					0.6	
LSD 0.05 for (Cult x S. Amend)				Ns					0.9					1.3	

Key: Soil Amend = Soil Amendment

Cult = Cultivar

Ctr = Control

Comp = Compost

Fer = Fertilizer

Pm = Poultry manure

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Discussion

The result of the experiment showed that there was high incidence of disease at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting of groundnut cultivars. The result was also consistently higher in Akure local cultivar which was closely followed by Samnut 23, while Samnut 22 had the least disease incidence of groundnut foliar disease. Disease severity was equally highest in Akure local at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting. This is likely because Samnut 21, Samnut 22 and Samnut 23 are all hybrid cultivars with disease resistance trait while Akure local is a local breed without any resistance trait (Auradha *et al.*, 2006). Soil amendment had a significant effect on incidence and severity of disease at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting. This is in agreement with Conn and Lazarovits (1999) which used a single manure application to reduce wilt and scab diseases of potato. Bailey and Lazarovits (2003) also reported that organic amendments, manures and composts with high nitrogen contents may suppress soil-borne diseases by releasing allelochemicals produced during product storage or by ultimate microbial decomposition. Control (zero amendment) result showed that there is highest incidence and severity of disease at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting which may be as a result of low nitrogen content and inadequate microbial decomposition to suppress soil-borne diseases (Bonanomi *et al.*, 2010). However, other amendments greatly reduced incidence and severity of disease in all the cultivars; poultry manure amendment recorded the least incidence and severity of disease at 4th, 6th and 8th weeks after planting. This agrees with the work done by Shakil *et al.* (2011) who used poultry manure, farm yard manure and cattle dung for soil amendment to manage root rot disease and to enhance agronomic characters of groundnut. Osunlaja (1990) confirmed that increased microbial population due to amendments played some role in disease suppression. This shows that poultry manure is an alternative mean of reducing foliar disease of groundnut. Planting of Samnut 21, Samnut 22 and Samnut 23 without any soil amendment reduced foliar disease of groundnut by 60, 40 and 74% compared with Akure local respectively. These cultivars are therefore recommended to farmers for good performance of groundnut in Southern Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Amongst foliar diseases of groundnut, *Cercospora* leaf spot is one of the most prevalent and widespread in humid agro climatic zone of Nigeria, however epidemics and losses in yield depends on cultivar, adaptation, environmental factors as well as cultural practices. Akure local is susceptible to leaf spot disease in the humid agro climatic zone of Nigeria. Akure local cultivar showed the highest level of disease incidence with leaves showing very severe infection at 6 WAP and completely infected at 8 WAP. This

shows it is more susceptible and vulnerable to leaf spot disease than any other cultivar, and therefore is least preferred in terms of leaf spot disease tolerance.

Application of poultry manure showed a high level of disease suppression. It recorded the least mean value for disease incidence and severity at 4, 6 and 8 WAP, followed by compost and NPK fertilizer. This is clear evidence that soil amendment could be an effective cultural control method for leaf spot diseases of groundnut. Application of poultry manure is therefore preferred to other soil amendments due to its effectiveness in reducing both disease incidence and disease severity of leaf spot on all four groundnut cultivars. Planting of Samnut 22 cultivar with application of Poultry manure gave the best result at 4, 6 and 8 WAP in terms of disease incidence and severity. It is therefore recommended ahead of other cultivars. This result shows that application of organic manure is an alternative way of controlling foliar diseases in groundnut cultivation.

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